

Resonance effect exhibited by tumor microenvironmental factors on tumor growth driven by correlated non-white Gaussian noises

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Abstract: The tumor response to the resonance effect exhibited by some surrounding random non-immunogenic micro-environmental factors modeled by additive and multiplicative colored (non-white) Gaussian noises is investigated. Using the Novikov theorem, Fox approach and the Anstaz of Hanggi, an analytic expression for approximate Fokker Planck equation for the time evolution of transition probability $p(x, t|x', t')$ is obtained. Numerical results reveal that the resonance effect exhibited by some non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors within the tumor site may be one of the factors responsible for their double edge effect of either promoting or inhibiting tumor growth.

Key words: Langevin Equation, Fokker-Planck Equation, Colored Noise, Tumor Microenvironment.

1. Introduction

In the recent decades, clinical and experimental investigations revealed a compelling evidence that tumors are resisting therapies, and therefore the need for further research especially on tumor microenvironment which plays a significant role on tumor initiation and progression [1–4]. Tumor microenvironment is a vicious environment that has a double-edge effect of either promoting or inhibiting tumor growth depending on some surrounding micro-processes within the tumor site [1]. Many biological and physical systems are subject to random environmental effects that can only be correctly understood from the probabilistic (stochastic) view point [5, 6], and tumor growth is such a biological system that responds to internal and external influences such as effects from the surrounding microenvironmental factors and external therapy.

The effect of external therapies such as radiotherapy and chemotherapy on tumor growth system have been studied using stochastic method [7–9], where the external therapies are assumed to restrain the tumor cell number given rise to negative additive noise, and the tumor responded to the therapeutic effect by generating a multiplicative internal noise on the tumor growth system. The internal noise that give rise to multiplicative noise is assumed to be generated by the internal mechanisms inside the tumor without contact to the external surrounding tumor microenvironmental factors which give rise to additive noise. Moreover, the internal multiplicative noise and external additive noise have different origin but are argued to be interrelated [10]. A more advanced stochastic model for tumor growth that takes into account tumor-immune interaction has been investigated and reported [11, 13–16]. In literature, the application of stochastic methods in the study of systems driven by noise have revealed patterns, complex behaviors and properties especially in biological,

physical and chemical systems [17–23]. The theoretical model equation is the Langevin stochastic equation and the corresponding Fokker Planck equation for the time evolution of the underlying transition probability $\rho(x, t|x', t')$ driving the system forward in time. Such theoretical descriptions have been used in different context to study the behavior of noise driven systems, where in most cases the noises are either Gaussian white or colored and in the form of additive or multiplicative. Tumor growth modeling is such a heuristic approach where some mathematical sigmoid function such as logistic and Gompertz equations are considered as deterministic models [11, 12].

In this paper, we advance the tumor model considered in [24] to be subject to resonance effect exhibited by some surrounding non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors within the tumor site, the resonance is due to the non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors vibrating with the same natural frequency as the frequency of some biological micro-processes. Such biological micro-processes include among others the signal transduction cellular activities, genetic instability, mutations and growth factors. In addition, the resonance effect will be mimicked by coupling a deterministic periodic impulse function to the additive colored noise representing the random non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors within the tumor site [22, 24, 25]. The paper is organized as follows, section 2 presents the model description in the form of Langevin stochastic equation, section 3 present the Approximate Fokker-Planck equation for the time evolution of probability density, section 4 present the steady state analysis, section 5 present the numerical results and discussion, and section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Model Description

The tumor model subject to random non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors with resonance effect is given by

$$\dot{x}(t) = f(x) + g_1(x) \cos A\eta(t) + g_2(x) \cos A\zeta(t), \quad (1)$$

where $f(x)$ is the logistic growth model, A is the amplitude parameter of the coupled deterministic periodic impulse function. The coupling periodic impulse function represent resonance effect due to the activities of some random biological micro-processes within the tumor microenvironment. Furthermore, the non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors effects within the tumor site are subje to the resonance effect. The resonance is due to vibrating effects from some biological micro-processes within the tumor microenvironment such as the signal transduction in cellular activity, genetic instability, mutations and growth factors [3, 26]. This means that the non-immunogenic tumor microenvironmental factors effect should have a periodic element, and by convention we consider the cosinoidal form $A \cos(\omega t)$, [21, 27]. Moreover, A is the amplitude of the periodic impulse signal and ω is the frequency. In our case, we assumed that the frequency of the coupled impulse signal is negligible, i.e, $\omega \rightarrow 0$, hence, there is enough time for the system to reach the steady state. Moreover, $\zeta(t)$ is the positive additive colored noise term representing the surrounding noisy non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors with resonance effect, and $\eta(t)$ is the multiplicative colored noise term representing tumor response to the surrounding non-immunogenic effect respectively. We consider the following assumptions for the tumor growth system $x(t)$:

- (i) The tumor growth $x(t)$ is a Markov process with transition probability given by

$$p(x_{n+1}, t_{n+1}|x_n, t_n; x_{n-1}, t_{n-1}; \dots; x_{n-i}, t_{n-i}; \dots; x_0, t_0) = p(x_{n+1}, t_{n+1}|x_n, t_n). \quad (2)$$

(ii) The process $x(t)$ is Ergodic, i.e., averaging over time is equivalent to averaging over the ensemble

$$\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T x(t) dt \equiv \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} xp(x) dx. \quad (3)$$

(iii) For an ordered sequence of time $\{t_0 < t_1 < t_2 < t_3 < \dots < t_{n-1} < t_n\}$, the tumor growth system $x(t)$ has an independent increment $\Delta x(t_i) = x(t_i) - x(t_{i-1})$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, such that the sequence $\{\Delta x(t_1), \Delta x(t_2), \dots, \Delta x(t_{n-1}), \Delta x(t_n)\}$ are independent stochastic variables.

(iv) $x(t_0) = 0$, no growth at time t_0 .

(v) The sequence of random increments $\Delta x(t_i) \sim N(0, Dt)$ for all $t > 0$, for which the underlying transition probability for the random increments satisfies the diffusion equation

$$\rho(x, t|x', t') = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi D(t-t')}} \exp\left[-\frac{(x-x_0)^2}{4D(t-t')}\right], \quad (4)$$

where (x', t') are increments for the spatial and temporal variables (x, t) , and D is the diffusion coefficient.

To analyze the tumor growth system $x(t)$ in Eq. (1), we consider the autocorrelation function of tumor growth $x(t)$ at time t with itself $x(t')$ at some time shift t' . Averaging the two time process $x(t)$ over a long time period yield the two time correlation function

$$\langle x(t)x(t') \rangle = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T x(t)x(t') dt. \quad (5)$$

In practice, the two time correlation function $\langle x(t)x(t') \rangle$ of the process $x(t)$ is approximated by the mean square value $\langle x(t)^2 \rangle$ of its displacement. Hence, the correlation function for the driven correlated additive and multiplicative noises $\eta(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ are given by

$$\langle \zeta(t)\zeta(t') \rangle = \frac{2\alpha \cos A}{\tau_1} \exp\left(-\frac{|t-t'|}{\tau_1}\right), \quad (6)$$

$$\langle \eta(t)\eta(t') \rangle = \frac{2\theta \cos A}{\tau_2} \exp\left(-\frac{|t-t'|}{\tau_2}\right). \quad (7)$$

The colored cross-correlation between the multiplicative colored noise $\eta(t)$ and additive colored noise $\zeta(t)$ is given by

$$\langle \eta(t)\zeta(t') \rangle = \langle \zeta(t)\eta(t') \rangle = \frac{2\lambda \cos A \sqrt{\alpha\theta}}{\tau_3} \exp\left(-\frac{|t-t'|}{\tau_3}\right), \quad (8)$$

where in Eq's. (6), (7) and (8) as the correlation times approaches zero, that is, $\tau_1 \rightarrow 0$, $\tau_2 \rightarrow 0$ and $\tau_3 \rightarrow 0$ the Gaussian white noise limits are recovered.

3. Approximate Fokker Planck Equation with Resonance Effect

To obtain the approximate Fokker Planck equation, we consider the fundamental stochastic Liouville equation corresponding to Eq. (1) [5, 30]

$$\partial_t \rho(x, t) = -\partial_x \{f(x) + \cos Ax\eta(t) + \cos A\zeta(t)\} \rho(x, t), \quad (9)$$

the function $\rho(x, t)$ in Eq.(9) is the probability density function for the possible realizations of the colored noises $\eta(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ respectively. Therefore, by lemma van Kampen in [29] which states that

$$P(x, t) = \langle \rho(x, t) \rangle, \quad (10)$$

where

$$\rho(x, t) = \delta(x(t) - x). \quad (11)$$

The probability distribution $P(x, t)$ in Eq. (10) is the average taking over the ensemble of $\rho(x, t)$ for the different possible realizations of the stochastic processes $\eta(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ in Eq. (9). Consider the numerical solution of Eq. (1) which represent an ensemble of different stochastic realizations each following a unique probability distribution $\rho(x, t)$ with a unique path as shown in figure 1 below, where the averaged probability

Figure 1. Ensemble of different stochastic realizations of Eq. (1)

distribution $P(x, t)$ satisfies the Fokker Planck equation interpreted in the sense of Stratonovich [29]. Moreover, dropping the coupled deterministic impulse function $\cos A$ in Eq. (9), and using the Van Kampen lemma in [29], an evolution equation for the probability density $P_{st}(x)$ is obtained. Therefore, Eq. (9) satisfies the general Fokker Planck equation of the form

$$\partial_t P(x, t) = -\partial_x f(x)P(x, t) - \partial_x g_1(x) \langle \eta(t) \delta(x(t) - x) \rangle - \partial_x g_2(x) \langle \zeta(t) \delta(x(t) - x) \rangle. \quad (12)$$

There is a change of notation for the probability density from $\rho(x, t)$ to $P(x, t)$ in Eq. (12) which is due to the Van Kampen lemma in Eq. (10). Moreover, for the averages in Eq. (12), we use the Novikov theorem, Fox

approach and the Ansatz of Hanggi to derive the Approximate Fokker-Planck equation for the tumor growth system [31–33]

$$\langle \gamma_i \Phi[\gamma_1, \gamma_2] \rangle = \int_0^t dt' \gamma_{ij} \frac{\delta \Phi[\gamma_1, \gamma_2]}{\delta \gamma_j}, \quad i, j = 1, 2 \quad (13)$$

where in Eq. (13), γ_1 and γ_2 corresponds to the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (colored) noises $\eta(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ respectively, γ_{11} and γ_{22} corresponds to the two-time self-correlation functions for the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (colored) noises $\eta(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ as given in Eq's. (6) and (7) respectively, and γ_{12} is the cross-correlation function given in Eq. (8). Thus for the present case we have

$$\langle \eta(t) \delta(x(t) - x) \rangle = \int_0^t dt' \langle \eta(t) \eta(t') \rangle \frac{\delta(\delta(x(t) - x))}{\delta \eta(t')} + \int_0^t dt' \langle \eta(t) \zeta(t') \rangle \frac{\delta(\delta(x(t) - x))}{\delta \zeta(t')}. \quad (14)$$

Following Hanggi-Ansatz approach, the Approximate Fokker-Planck equation in steady state regime is obtained, [33]

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \eta(t) \delta(x(t) - x) \rangle = & - \frac{\alpha}{1 - \tau_1 \left[f(x_s)' - \frac{g_1(x_s)'}{g_1(x_s)} f(x_s) \right]} \partial_x g_1(x) P(x, t) \\ & - \frac{\lambda \sqrt{\alpha \theta}}{1 - \tau_3 \left[f(x_s)' - \frac{g_1(x_s)'}{g_1(x_s)} f(x_s) \right]} \partial_x g_2(x) P(x, t), \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

and similarly

$$\langle \zeta(t) \delta(x(t) - x) \rangle = \int_0^t dt' \langle \zeta(t) \zeta(t') \rangle \frac{\delta(\delta(x(t) - x))}{\delta \zeta(t')} + \int_0^t dt' \langle \zeta(t) \eta(t') \rangle \frac{\delta(\delta(x(t) - x))}{\delta \eta(t')}, \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \zeta(t) \delta(x(t) - x) \rangle = & - \frac{\theta}{1 - \tau_2 \left[f(x_s)' - \frac{g_2(x_s)'}{g_2(x_s)} f(x_s) \right]} \partial_x g_2(x) P(x, t) \\ & - \frac{\lambda \sqrt{\alpha \theta}}{1 - \tau_3 \left[f(x_s)' - \frac{g_2(x_s)'}{g_2(x_s)} f(x_s) \right]} \partial_x g_1(x) P(x, t). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Thus by bringing back the deterministic impulse function $\cos A$, Eq. (15) and (17) respectively becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \eta(t) \delta(x(t) - x) \rangle = & - \frac{\alpha \cos A}{1 - \tau_1 \left[f(x_s)' - \frac{g_1(x_s)'}{g_1(x_s)} f(x_s) \right]} \partial_x g_1(x) P(x, t) \\ & - \frac{\lambda \cos A \sqrt{\alpha \theta}}{1 - \tau_3 \left[f(x_s)' - \frac{g_1(x_s)'}{g_1(x_s)} f(x_s) \right]} \partial_x g_2(x) P(x, t), \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \zeta(t) \delta(x(t) - x) \rangle = & - \frac{\theta \cos A}{1 - \tau_2 \left[f(x_s)' - \frac{g_2(x_s)'}{g_2(x_s)} f(x_s) \right]} \partial_x g_2(x) P(x, t) \\ & - \frac{\lambda \cos A \sqrt{\alpha \theta}}{1 - \tau_3 \left[f(x_s)' - \frac{g_2(x_s)'}{g_2(x_s)} f(x_s) \right]} \partial_x g_1(x) P(x, t). \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Therefore substituting Eq's. (18) and (19) into Eq. (12), the Approximate Fokker Planck equation to the Langevin equation (Eq.(1)) is obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t P(x, t) = & -\partial_x f(x)P(x, t) + \frac{\alpha \cos A}{M_1} \partial_x g_1(x) \partial_x g_1(x) P(x, t) \\ & + \frac{\theta \cos A}{M_2} \partial_x g_2(x) \partial_x g_2(x) P(x, t) \\ & + \frac{2\lambda \cos A \sqrt{\alpha\theta}}{M_3} [\partial_x g_1(x) \partial_x g_2(x) + \partial_x g_2(x) \partial_x g_1(x)] P(x, t), \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where

$$M_i = 1 - \tau_i \left[f(x_s)' - \frac{g_j(x_s)'}{g_j(x_s)} f(x_s) \right], \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \quad j = 1, 2. \quad (21)$$

Consequently, in Eq. (21), $x_s = a/b$ is the steady state value for the function $f(x)$ and τ_i are the associated correlation times and cross-correlation time respectively. In addition, Eq. (20) is only valid under the condition that $M_i > 0$. Thus, from Eq. (20) the analytic expression for the diffusion term is given as

$$G(x) = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha \cos A}{1 + a\tau_1} x^2 + \frac{2\lambda \cos A \sqrt{\alpha\theta}}{1 + a\tau_3} x + \frac{\theta \cos A}{1 + a\tau_2}}. \quad (22)$$

4. Steady State Distribution with Resonance Effect

The steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ for the tumor growth system is obtained by interpreting the Approximate Fokker Planck equation in Eq. (20) with (21) in the sense of Stratonovich [29]

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} P(x, t) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[A(x) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} B(x) \right] P(x, t), \quad (23)$$

where $A(x)$ is the modified drift term and $B(x)$ is the diffusion term respectively given as

$$A(x) = f(x) + G(x) \frac{d}{dx} G(x), \quad (24)$$

$$B(x) = G(x)^2. \quad (25)$$

Thus, from Eq. (24) and (25) we have explicit expressions for the drift and diffusion terms as

$$A(x) = \left(a - \frac{\alpha \sin A}{1 + a\tau_1} \right) x - bx^2 - \frac{\lambda \sin A \sqrt{\alpha\theta}}{1 + a\tau_2}, \quad (26)$$

$$B(x) = \frac{\alpha \cos A}{1 + a\tau_1} x^2 + \frac{2\lambda \cos A \sqrt{\alpha\theta}}{1 + a\tau_3} x + \frac{\theta \cos A}{1 + a\tau_2}. \quad (27)$$

Moreover, Eq. (20) can be written in terms of the conservation equation for probability. Thus, the probability current density $J(x)$ for the tumor growth system is given by

$$\begin{aligned} J(x) = & \left[\left(a - \frac{\alpha \sin A}{1 + a\tau_1} \right) x - bx^2 - \frac{\lambda \sin A \sqrt{\alpha\theta}}{1 + a\tau_2} \right] P(x, t) \\ & - \left[\frac{\alpha \cos A}{1 + a\tau_1} x^2 + \frac{2\lambda \cos A \sqrt{\alpha\theta}}{1 + a\tau_3} x + \frac{\theta \cos A}{1 + a\tau_2} \right] \partial_x P(x, t). \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Tumor growth is a biological process that evolve at a time and continuously progress over a long time interval, therefore we consider $t \rightarrow \infty$. It is therefore assumed that at steady state, the transition probability driving the system forward is time translation invariant, i.e, $\partial_t P(x, t) = 0$, and the rate of flow of probability is independent of the system variable x . Therefore, integrating Eq. (28) the steady state current is obtained

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\left(a - \frac{\alpha \sin A}{1 + a\tau_1} \right) x - bx^2 - \frac{\lambda \sin A \sqrt{\alpha\theta}}{1 + a\tau_2} \right] P_{st}(x) \\ & - \left[\frac{\alpha \cos A}{1 + a\tau_1} x^2 + \frac{2\lambda \cos A \sqrt{\alpha\theta}}{1 + a\tau_3} x + \frac{\theta \cos A}{1 + a\tau_2} \right] \partial_x P_{st}(x) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

An analytic expression for the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ of the tumor growth system $x(t)$ is obtained by solving Eq. (29) with reflecting boundary condition. Moreover, we consider the difference in time scale to be insignificant, therefore the self-correlation times τ_1, τ_2 and cross-correlation time τ_3 are equal [24], i.e, $\tau_1 = \tau_2 = \tau_3 = \tau$. Finally, an explicit expression for the steady state distribution is obtained

$$P_{st}(x) = NB(x)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \exp \left[-\frac{U(x)}{\alpha \cos A} \right], \quad (30)$$

where N is the normalization constant given by

$$N = \left[\int B(x)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \exp \left(\frac{-U(x)}{\alpha \cos A} \right) dx \right]^{-1}, \quad (31)$$

$B(x)$ is the diffusion term and $U(x)$ is the effective potential given by

$$U(x) = b(1 + a\tau)x - E_1 \ln \left| \left(\frac{x + \lambda \sqrt{\frac{\theta}{\alpha}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\theta(1+a\tau)}{\alpha}(1-\lambda^2)}} \right)^2 + 1 \right| - E_2 \arctan \left(\frac{x + \lambda \sqrt{\frac{\theta}{\alpha}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\theta(1+a\tau)}{\alpha}(1-\lambda^2)}} \right), \quad (32)$$

where in Eq. (32) α is the multiplicative noise strength, θ is the additive noise strength, τ is the strength of the correlation time, λ is the cross-correlation strength between noises, A is the strength of the periodic impulse and E_1, E_2 are given by

$$E_1 = a - \frac{\alpha \sin A}{1 + a\tau} + 2b\lambda \sqrt{\frac{\theta}{\alpha}}, \quad (33)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{\left(a - \frac{\alpha \sin A}{1 + a\tau} + 2b\lambda \sqrt{\frac{\theta}{\alpha}} \right) \lambda \sqrt{\frac{\theta}{\alpha}} + \frac{\lambda \sin A \sqrt{\alpha\theta}}{1 + a\tau} - \frac{b\theta}{\alpha}}{\sqrt{\frac{\theta(1+a\tau)}{\alpha}(1-\lambda^2)}}. \quad (34)$$

5. Results Discussion

To analyze the steady state properties for the tumor response to the resonance effect exhibited by some surrounding random non-immunogenic micro-environmental factors, the numerical simulation for the steady

Figure 2. Plot of the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ at varying tumor response parameter α at low resonance effect strength $A = 1.0$

Figure 3. Plot of the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ at varying tumor response parameter α at moderately low resonance effect strength $A = 4.0$

state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ in Eq. (30) against the tumor population is done. In addition to the complexity induced by the correlation time effect τ on the tumor growth system as reported in [24], the tumor response to the resonance effect which is due to the random non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors within the tumor site vibrating with the same natural frequency as the frequency of some micro-processes within the tumor microenvironment, such as the signal transduction pathways and which may lead to some additional complexity [1]. Figures [2-5] depict the tumor response to the non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors resonance effect within the tumor site, and it is observed through the figures that the tumor response with parameter α to the microenvironmental resonance effect alternate with increasing impulse strength value A . This is evident in Figures 2 and 4 having different values of A , i.e., $A = 1.0$ and 8.0 respectively but with extremely similar

Figure 4. Plot of the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ at varying tumor response parameter α at moderately high resonance effect strength $A = 8.0$

Figure 5. Plot of the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ at varying tumor response parameter α at high resonance effect strength $A = 12.0$

numerical results. Likewise, Figures 3 and 5 with different values of impulse strength A , i.e., $A = 4.0$ and 12.0 but with similar numerical results. This indicated that the non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors vibrating due to resonance effect from surrounding vibrating micro-processes within the tumor site is another source of complexity on the tumor growth system.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, tumor response to the resonance effect likely exhibited by some surrounding random non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors within the tumor site is investigated. The resonance effects are due to the non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors within the tumor site vibrating with the same natural

frequency as the frequency of some vibrating biological micro-processes within the tumor microenvironment, such micro-processes among others includes signaling pathways in cellular activity and genetic instability. The result indicated that the tumor response to the resonance effect with parameter α alternate between promoting tumor growth to reducing tumor growth at increasing impulse strength A as shown in figure 2. This remarkable property indicated that the resonance effect exhibited by some non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors within the tumor site may be one of the factors responsible for their double edge effect of either promoting or inhibiting tumor growth.

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